

Principles of Inclusive Education

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Abstract: *This article provides information about the principles of inclusive education. Inclusive education seeks to develop a methodology aimed at educating children with various needs. Inclusive education involves the development of a comprehensive approach to teaching aimed at meeting various needs.*

Keywords: *inclusive education, principle, disabled, need, special education, limited opportunities, principle.*

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Inclusive education (derived from the English word inclusive, inclusion – to integrate, to harmonize, to cover, to cover) is an educational system that represents the inclusion of children with disabilities and healthy children in the general education process, aimed at eliminating barriers between them, and at adapting children and adolescents with special needs to social life, regardless of their developmental disabilities or economic difficulties. The terms “inclusive” and “integrated” are often used interchangeably. However, there is a big difference between these concepts. Placing a child with disabilities in ordinary conditions is the first step towards integration. The inclusion of children with disabilities in general education institutions is called “inclusive” or “integrated” education worldwide. That is, it is an education that aims to treat all children equally, to value and develop any opportunities they have, regardless of their nationality, race, skin color, social origin, family status in society, source, material and spiritual condition, physical or mental development.

If teaching and learning in the implementation of inclusive education is somewhat effective and productive, then not only children with disabilities, but all children will win. Inclusive education schools protect the individual rights of children to receive education. Such an approach eliminates and reduces discrimination because children realize that they are individuals with different needs in the process of learning in the process of communicating with each other. The views of the famous Eastern scholars Ibn Sina, Imam Bukhari, Abu Nasr Farooqi, Alisher Navoi, and Abdulla Avloni on the goals of education and the impact of education on the development of each child's personality are the methodological basis for the development of inclusive education. For a very long time, it was considered effective to educate children in special segregated educational institutions compared to general education institutions. The issue of education and upbringing of children with disabilities is becoming one of the most pressing issues today. Special education has developed as an educational system for children with disabilities. This education is built on the assumption that the needs of children with disabilities cannot be met in general education institutions. Special education operates all over the world in the form of schools or boarding schools, as well as as small parts of general education schools. "The education system should be like this," writes L.S. Vygotsky, who believes that the task of raising a disabled child is to compensate for the child's defects and ensure his integration into life, and for this it is necessary to create such an education system that a child in

need of special assistance can develop comprehensively during the learning process. That is, L.S. Vygotsky recognized the organization of an education system that combines general and special education, the education of children in need of special assistance in the general education system.

The role and place of the inclusive education system in the development of society requires the following tasks to be solved: creating the necessary psychological, pedagogical, and correctional conditions for the education of children and adolescents with disabilities in educational institutions, implementing general education programs and correctional work aimed at their capabilities, and ensuring their spiritual development and social adaptation; guaranteeing the right of students to equality in education; meeting the needs of disabled and healthy children with the active participation of society and the family, and early adaptation to social life; realizing the right of children and adolescents with disabilities to live without being separated from their families; forming a friendly and loving attitude towards children and adolescents with disabilities in society. This also has a negative impact on parents. Although children with disabilities cannot complete tasks and tasks as quickly and perfectly as children with normal development, they can do them to the extent possible. Protecting the rights of the child and having a positive attitude towards them is an important method of upbringing.

Principles of inclusive education:

1. The value of a person does not depend on his abilities and achievements;
2. Everyone has the ability to think and feel;
3. Everyone has the ability to hear and communicate;
4. Everyone needs each other.
5. A person's full and true education can only be achieved through real cooperation.
6. Everyone needs the support of their peers.
7. The success of all learners is not due to their inability to do something, but to their ability to do something.

Sending specialists to work closely with the parents of children.

Principles: Basic principles of inclusive education. The implementation of an education system always requires a basis in certain laws, regulations, and principles.

The implementation of an inclusive education system is based on the following principles:

- 1) Recognition of inclusive education.
- 2) The principle of inclusive education being open to all.
- 3) The principle of connectivity.
- 4) The principle of decentralization.
- 5) The principle of an integrated approach in inclusive education.
- 6) The principle of flexibility in inclusive education. 7) The principle of competence. The principle of recognition of inclusive education. The content of this principle has been adopted in several global declarations and resolutions. They have been recognized by many countries of the world. However, to date, there are many problems in implementing them. In some countries, when laws or resolutions are adopted on general education, the issue of education of children with disabilities is not included in it. The fact is that since 1990, a number of global declarations and resolutions have been adopted on the education of children with special needs in the system of general education institutions. They have been recognized by many countries of the world. However, to this day, there

are many problems in implementing them. In some countries, when laws or resolutions are adopted on general education, the issue of education of children with disabilities is not included in it. In conclusion, the principle of inclusive education is that it should be open to all. Over the past twenty years, significant work has been done on the education of children with special needs in the system of general education institutions.

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